

Second Language Learning

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Abstract

Human beings distinguished with languages, speaking, talking and conversation. In this wide Information technology spread, it can be observed the expand of English language exactly through all the world. That is also noticed in most of the countries of the Middle East. The second language learning is more important than the mother tongue, because the people are contacting each other through different continents, countries, cities and villages. This contacting with his\her mobile in his hand, his pocket or her bag. The person need at least two languages to communicate with others around him or her.

Introduction

Humans at the last centuries Had a lot of inventions. They call it names according to their nationalities and languages, e.g the electric machines with its different usages. Also in the past there was not a car or a plane or even a train all of these were inventions for human beings. Thus this was traced in all languages for example a telephone becomes a mobile and it can be named in all around the world in many words. In one language you can say many words to contact, to phone, to ring, to call and all these shed lights to language used and users also the language usage itself.

The connection between people in different languages, the writer reveals it as connection not even CONTACT, because this is as if you speak to your family at home not just a stranger.

So, the controlling of contact here becomes stronger through different medias. In this behaviour can be in sane like switching the light on a hacker pucker -1. It is of course strange to say this.

Let us back to the title of the paper(second language learning) through this integration it is cold to feel not hot weather or because repeating the discussion again of not having only two languages or knowing more is critical assumption

According to the diacritic movements through a real life problem to a situation which put people in danger like the hectic follow up or dangerous encyclopedia through adjusting light to daily behaviour. The feeling of withdrawn is so urgent among hypnotical discam.

It perhaps throw the writer in a deep situation of convincing the others that they talk or they have to speak several languages (people actually find themselves like this). One of the ancestors for example can speak Arabic and study in school & university English and have a friend who speak other language which is a peripheral language that have no code or even no speakers nowadays.

The jemishtat-2way in knowing other language is a great deal of hypocrisy design that look like contacting your face with eagerness to go and come Forward and backward.

The taste of language is special due to the fulfilling of speaking itself. So, it can be also to be tasted like you are eating a shawarma or a burger hufnuf.

Then the feeling itself you feel satisfied dangerously wondered through a vacuum road testing yourself in grammar and vocabulary itself, here is the hint measuring your ability to hang on such designs speaking quacity-3 in a cave

And not just looking but watching the drawings of your spelling forming sentences it is what is called a SKILL. A skill can be shaped like training your mind or your body but not training souls.

Let us negotiate it one by one.

Firstly training mind this is step by step moving on knowledge through the steam of life.

Secondly training body in different sports from walking till difficult and tough sports like taekwondo or karate.

Thirdly training souls we can say mainly through garaging -4and this specially we call praying.

Falling under the estimation of controlling the whole world by one language is not strange, but we can say it is egoistic. As the performance of one land and one population of a country, the writer can extract the behaviour of humans from their speech. It doesn't give another background but the real formation of the person. Therefore

here the writer want to understand whether stablishing a continuous learning for the generations not only the environment when a person needs to study a language. The writer here is not going to give hints or things like this, because it is the polite way people learn to talk other languages. Here is a thing indicate on the deserve of being human. If this corner give us a way to talk about how to be polite in speaking in a language this the thing itself. Not just because the writer is a teacher but basically the people find the polite person more attractive than the wicked who he or she uses bad words.

Under certain circumstances the second language learning needs of course environment, because a person or as a case it can be said students need to know the background of the environment itself. Here it is being repeated environment, because an individual can not live with out knowing the others let alone knowing other languages (people and their languages and try to learn other languages).

Let us have a person e.g the way he or she is speaking standing or sitting the expressions of the face the sound of the tone, you will know immediately he speaks politely or no.

Second language learning interpretability needs a hint of strategy that surrounding the student not effecting his or her traditions or customs or even culture, but behavior and this is the thing which needed to be seen (different cultures and different significant points).

Learning a second language really the researcher have to focus on a certain clue it is motivation a sharp arrow indicate need towards learning. So this is the mass of recommending to study. Egzoferic-5mass , When the writer talk about motivation this is because it is the real reason behind doing some work or studying according to as mentioned before the ability and the skill.

Language learning and language acquisition as Krashen said two hands for one thing specially in adapting a way to communicate between people. So Krashen went in his first hypothesis to differentiate between learning and acquiring. Acquiring is said to be from childhood recent researches indicate that (from an extract) :- (babies begin this journey earlier than you might think. Studies show that Fetuses in the third trimester can hear and distinguish vowel sounds and rhythms of their native language versus a foreign language.) This supply us with information that children began to hear from the start of the first pulse in the uterus of the mother. Not just hearing but also sense the pulse and the warmth of his or her mother. So here is another extract (As babies grow they start understanding the meaning of common nouns around 6-9 months of age , even before they start speaking.) This clear in children one year old and differ from a child to another and even whether male or female. Let us see the third extract (first language learning is instinctive and unconscious. Children learn by living with their parents, who naturally talk to them everyday topics.) Of course a person can not recall when she or he started to talk or even speak like his or her parents until he or she has their own type of speech according to their thinking let us be back again to the ability and skill.

As a result for first birth, if you are born in Korea you will speak Korean, in England you will speak English. One of the scholars evidences in that the environment have effect on the babies. They can bring one child from England and the other child from China. They can replace them as the following :- the English child with Chinese parents in China (environment), And the Chinese Child with English parents in England (environment). So at age five the Chinese child will speak English, and the British child will speak Chinese. It will be great evidence that the environment has the direct indication on human beings lives.

Let us be back to Krashen who said that acquiring from childhood and learning in schools and institutes. So here learning is the business whether the person is a native-like speaker or non native speaker.

((LEARN)) this is the thing the writer is pointing out.

The origin of the word:-

Old English *leornian* 'learn' (in Middle English also 'teach'), of West Germanic origin; related to German *lernen*, also to **lore**.-1

The redagger of human beings as a proper one can learn everyday from all the people elder or younger, because this is life learn how to do things adequately, how to learn from mistakes and here it's being concentrated on how to learn a language.

To learn a language of course the person has two things ability and skill it has been mentioned before. Let us put it step by step. It can begin with conversations then writing which is the hard task of course.

Conversations for example in how greeting people and how to say goodbye, how to deal in a shop for example a grocery shop, What are the names of vegetables, trying to count to know the currency itself how many and how much.

Then Writing it goes mainly through alphabetical order, how to write them then how to connect them to make words, what is the meaning of the words and how to use them in a proper sentence. Mean while the grammar how to put words in a sentence perfectly to give the correct meaning . Of course sentence plus sentence will give a paragraph, A paragraph plus a paragraph will give a composition then essay then a topic. A topic plus another topic a book. That is the thing in learning. But ((LEARN)) is a big word in itself concentrating on where ,why and how this is the main perfect thing. According to a significant board line a person can learn good things also can learn bad things. The same in language a person can learn good language and speak it, also can learn bad language and speak it. Then behavior is the same steps. It can be put according to our terms. The input of

the learner within a social context gives the output from the interlanguage of the learner. And this is the scale of life mandatory behavior for skills.

The writer here is trying to antagonize the concept from the dictionary meaning.

Learn -2 meaning in Oxford Dictionary:-

1. To gain knowledge or skill by studying, from experience, from being taught, etc.

- **learn something to learn a language/skill/trade**
- *He had the opportunity to learn English in Australia.*
- **learn (something) from somebody/something I learned a lot from my father.**
- *Everyone in the class had the opportunity to learn from each other.*
- **learn (something) from doing something** *You can learn a great deal just from watching other players.*
- **learn (about something)** *She's very keen to learn about Japanese culture.*
- *The book is about how children learn.*
- *She received no training but quickly **learnt on the job** (= while doing the job).*
- **learn to do something** *He's learning to play the trumpet.*
- *Most people learn to read as children.*
- **learn how to do something** *Today we learnt how to use the new software.*
- **learn what, where, etc...** *Students need to learn what to do in an emergency.*

2. **Learn something** to study and repeat something in order to be able to remember it

SYNONYM **memorize**

- *I **learnt** the poem **by heart**.*
- *We have to learn one of Hamlet's speeches for school tomorrow.*
- *You'll have to learn your lines by next week.*

3. To gradually change your attitudes about something so that you behave in a different way

- *Some people never learn, do they?*
- **learn from something** *I'm sure she'll learn from her mistakes.*
- *Why do people so often fail to **learn from experience**?*
- **learn (that)...** *He'll just have to learn (that) he can't always have his own way.*
- *They soon learn that bad behaviour is a sure-fire way of getting attention.*
- **learn to do something** *They soon **learned to love** living in the countryside.*
- *I soon learned not to ask too many questions.*

4. To become aware of something by hearing about it from somebody else SYNONYM **discover**

- **learn of something** *I first learnt of his death many years later.*
- **learn about something** *We only learned about the problems in May of this year.*
- **learn (that)...** *We were very **surprised to learn (that)** she had got married again.*
- **learn who, what, etc...** *We only learned who the new teacher was a few days ago.*
- **learn something** *How did they react when they learned the news?*
- **it is learned that...** *It has been learned that 500 jobs are to be lost at the factory.*

Idioms

know/learn/find something to your cost

1. To know something because of something unpleasant that has happened to you
 - *She is a tough competitor, as I know to my cost.*

learn (something) the hard way

1. To find out how to behave by learning from your mistakes or from unpleasant experiences, rather than from being told

learn your lesson

1. To learn what to do or not to do in the future because you have had a bad experience in the past

show somebody/know/learn the ropes

1. (*informal*) to show somebody/know/learn how a particular job should be done

you live and learn

1. Used to express surprise at something new or unexpected you have been told

NOTES

- 1- Becoming like a pilot
- 2- From Albanian ((we))
- 3- Translate from Hmong Quantity
- 4- Dutch Karaj
- 5- Egzoferic From Romanian Astonished but the writer here means an outside mass that is astonishing people

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